

Synthesis of 2-(5'-Methoxy-4'H-pyran-4'-one)-2'-yl-chromone and Chromanone

Monojit Ghosal and D. N. Chaudhury

The synthesis of the title compounds is described.

Our success in evolving a simple preparative method¹ for comenaldehyde methyl ether (I) prompted us to investigate the synthesis of some oxygen heterocycles. The well-known synthetic sequence involving condensation of aromatic aldehydes with *o*-hydroxyacetophenones and transformation of the resulting *o*-hydroxychalcones to flavanones and flavones has been adopted, substituting the aldehyde (I) for aromatic aldehydes, to afford analogous compounds having a γ -pyrone ring at the 2-position of chromanone and chromone nucleus.

As an exploratory experiment, comenaldehyde methyl ether (I) was condensed with acetophenone in presence of diethylamine or zinc chloride in acetic acid to afford colorless crystals of β -(5-methoxy-4H-pyran-4-one)-2-yl-acrylophenone (II). Likewise, condensation with *o*-hydroxyacetophenone in presence of diethylamine furnished pale yellow crystalline β -(5-methoxy-4H-pyran-4-one)-2-yl-*o*-hydroxyacrylophenone (III). The usual condensing agents, alkali solution², pyridine³, piperidine³, and hydrogen chloride⁴ failed to bring about the desired condensation and the products obtained were intractable in every case. The *o*-hydroxychalcone analogue (III), on treatment with selenium dioxide⁵ in refluxing ethylene glycol monomethyl ether, yielded the flavone analogue, 2-(5'-methoxy-4'H-pyran-4'-one)-2'-yl-chromone (IV) as yellow crystals. Cyclisation of (III) with phosphoric acid⁵ furnished the flavanone analogue, 2-(5'-methoxy-4'H-pyran-4'-one)-2'-yl-chromanone (V) as shining yellow-brown crystals.

Condensation of the aldehyde (I) with 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyacetophenone (peonol)⁶ in presence of diethylamine did not, however, take the normal course. Three unidentified crystalline products, A, B and C, were obtained under different conditions of temperature and reaction time. Each of the compounds (A) and (B) showed colour reaction with ferric chloride, but their analyses did not fit the expected *o*-hydroxychalcone analogue nor for any of the other possible condensation products⁷. The analyses of the compound (C),

1. Ghosal and Chaudhury, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 244.
2. Elderfield, "Heterocyclic Compounds", J. Wiley, 1950, Vol. II, pp. 346-350.
3. Order and Lindwall, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1945, 10, 128.
4. Mahal and Venkataraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 569.
5. Tatsuta, *J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1942, 63, 935; *Chem. Abst.*, 1947, 41, 4123.
6. Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 51, 260.
7. Rodd, "Chemistry of Carbon Compounds", Elsevier, 1956, Vol. IIIB, p. 1183.

which developed no colour with ferric chloride, did not correspond to any of the possible flavanone analogues² either.

*EXPERIMENTAL

β-(5-Methoxy-4-H-pyran-4-one)-2-yl-acetylphenone (II).—(a) C. menaldehyde methyl ether (I) (0.25 g.), acetophenone (0.25 ml), and diethylamine (5 drops) in etheral (10 ml) were made a homogeneous solution by warming and then left at the room temperature for 24 hours. Crystals separating were collected and recrystallised from methanol to afford the pure product (II) (25 mg.) as colorless irregular prisms, m.p. 186-87°. (Found: C, 69.71; H, 4.51. C₁₅H₁₂O₄ requires C, 70.31; H, 4.70%).

(b). To a solution of fused zinc chloride (0.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) were added the compound (I) (0.3 g.) and acetophenone (0.4 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 30 minutes, cooled, diluted with water, and left overnight in the frigidaire when a white solid (0.15 g.), m.p. 181°, separated. It was collected, washed with water, and crystallised twice from methanol to afford the pure product (II), m.p. 187°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained under (a).

β-(5-Methoxy-4H-pyran-4-one)-2-yl-*o*-hydroxyacetylphenone (III).—The compound (I) (2 g.) and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (2 ml) in ethanol (25 ml) along with diethylamine (10 drops) were heated at 60-70° for 20 minutes. After dilution with water (50 ml) it was left overnight in an ice-chest to furnish pale yellow crystals (1.3 g.), m.p. 165-66°. Crystallisation from ethanol afforded the pure product (III) as pale yellow needles, m.p. 165-66.5°. It showed a deep violet colour with an aquo-ethanolic ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 65.76; H, 4.89. C₁₅H₁₂O₅ requires C, 66.18; H, 4.41%).

*All m.p.s are uncorrected. Microanalyses by Drs. Weiler and Straus, Oxford, England.

2-(5'-*Methoxy-4'H-pyran-4'-one*)-2'-yl-*chromone* (IV).—The preceding ketone (III) (0.5 g.) and selenium dioxide (0.5 g.) in ethylene glycol monomethyl ether (10 ml) were refluxed for 10 hours. The solution was cooled, filtered, diluted with water to turbidity, and left in a frigidaire overnight when a yellow crystalline precipitate (0.2 g.), m.p. 214-15°, was obtained. It was purified by crystallisation from glacial acetic acid and a few drops of water as yellow needles, m.p. 218°. It developed no colour with aquo-ethanolic FeCl_3 . (Found: C, 66.10; H, 3.86. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 66.66; H, 3.70%.)

2-(5'-*Methoxy-4'H-pyran-4'-one*)-2-yl-*chromanone* (V).—Phosphoric acid (3 drops, d 1.8) was added to a suspension of compound (III) (0.3 g.) in ethanol (10 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 48 hours. The solution was cooled, diluted with water to turbidity, and left in a frigidaire. The solid (50 ml), m.p. 180-81°, was crystallised twice from methanol to furnish the pure product (V) as yellow-brown plates, m.p. 198-99°. Its ethanolic solution did not develop any colour with ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 65.76; H, 4.69. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 66.18; H, 4.41%.)

Compound (A).—The compound (I) (0.5 g.) and peonol¹⁶ (0.7 g.) in ethanol (10 ml) with 5 drops of diethylamine were heated on a steam bath for 80 minutes. After dilution with water it was left in a frigidaire overnight when unchanged peonol (0.4 g.) was recovered. The filtrate, on keeping for 7 days, deposited crystals (0.15 g.), m.p. 152-53°. It was purified by recrystallisation from ethanol to afford *compound (A)* as brownish yellow needles, m.p. 155-56°. It developed a pink colour with aquo-ethanolic ferric chloride, gradually deepening to brown-red. (Found: C, 59.06; H, 5.0%.)

Compound (B).—The compound (I) (0.2 g.) and peonol (0.3 g.) with diethylamine (5 drops) in ethanol (5 ml) were refluxed on a steam bath for 4 hours. On cooling, yellow crystals, m.p. 206-208°, separating were recrystallised from acetic acid to furnish *compound (B)* as pale yellow needles, m.p. 211.5°. It developed a red-brown colour with aquo-ethanolic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 62.28; H, 4.96%.)

Compound (C).—Compound (I) (1.0 g.) and peonol (1.1 g.) in ethanol (15 ml) with diethylamine (5 drops) were heated at 55-60° for 20 minutes. It was then cooled, diluted with water just to turbidity, and left overnight. Unchanged peonol (0.7 g.), which gradually deposited, was filtered and the filtrate was further diluted with an equal volume of water and set aside for 15 days. The solid separating was collected and refluxed with ethanol in which it was insoluble. The residue (0.2 g.) after hot filtration was crystallised twice from acetic acid-water to afford the pure *compound (C)* as colorless crystals, m.p. 219°. It gave no colour reaction with aquo-ethanolic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 57.57; H, 4.55%.)